

Title:

Accuracy Enhancement of Machine Tools by Virtual Machining Systems

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Abstract: Actual machining processes can be analyzed and modified in virtual environments in order to increase accuracy and efficiency of part manufacturing. So, more added value in part production can be achieved by analyzing as well as modifying actual machining processes using virtual machining systems.

Keywords: Virtual Machining, Accuracy of produced parts

1- Introduction

Virtual manufacturing systems carry out the simulation of manufacturing processes in digital environment in order to increase accuracy as well as productivity in part production [1]. This can provide useful means for products to be manufactured without the need of physical testing on the shop floor. As a result, the time and cost of part production can be decreased [2].

2- Applications

- In order to achieve the best accuracy in the produced part, the part is modeled and produced in a computer simulation environment with predicted errors [2], [4].
- Errors of actual machined parts can be simulated in virtual environments in order to be analyzed and compensated [2].
- Efficiency of part manufacturing can be improved by analyzing and optimizing the production methods [3].

References

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